

STUDIES IN COMPLEX FORMATION WITH COLLOIDAL MERCURI-
SULPHOSALICYLATE. PART III. COMPLEX URANYL
MERCURISULPHOSALICYLATE

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Potentiometric, conductometric and colorimetric studies of the complex formation between uranyl nitrate and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate show that only one complex containing the reactants in the ratio of 1 : 1 is formed at p_H 4.5. During the complex formation, the phenolic hydrogen is displaced and the co-ordination takes place between the oxygen atoms of phenolic and carboxyl groups.

In Parts I and II (Singh and Prakash, this *Journal*, 1957, 35, 197, 807) the studies of complex formation of mercurisulphosalicylate with beryllium and aluminium have been reported. Physico-chemical studies on the formation of uranyl mercurisulphosalicylate complex in solution have been reported herein.

Sulphosalicylic acid forms a solid compound corresponding to the composition $(C_6H_3-OH-SO_3-COO)_2U$ with uranium (St. Weil and St. Rozenblum, *Bull. Trans. Inst. Pharm.*, Poland, 1902, 1, 1). Wienland and Häger (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 180, 193) prepared a large number of complex compounds of uranyl ion with salicylic acid. Uranyl complexes with citric, lactic, malic and tartaric acids have been investigated by Feldman *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2315, 3593; 1954, 76, 2114). Anderson *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1949, 71, 909) have investigated the complex formation of uranyl ion with sulphosalicylic acid spectrophotometrically. They have shown that a mixture containing the reactants has a maximum absorption at a p_H range of 4.00-4.70 at 444m μ . Using Job's method (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113) of continued variation, they have found that only one complex containing uranyl and sulphosalicylic acid in the ratio of 1 : 1 is formed. No definite structure has been suggested, but the co-ordination has been assumed to be between the carboxyl and sulphonic groups.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of uranyl nitrate were prepared by direct weighing of Baker's analysed sample of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and dissolving in water. Fresh solutions were employed to avoid effects due to hydrolysis.

Standard solutions of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate and its monosodium salt were prepared as described earlier (Singh and Prakash, *loc. cit.*, p. 197).

All measurements were made at a constant temperature of $32^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The specific conductivity and p_H measurements were made as described previously (*loc. cit.*).

The colorimetric measurements were made with a Klett-Sommerson photoelectric colorimeter, using Klett filters Ks 47(445-505 m μ) and Ks 54 (520-580 m μ).

The procedure adopted here was the same as described previously (*loc. cit.*). The mixture solutions with varying amounts of alkali were allowed to stand for 24 hours when precipitation occurred as a result of the attainment of equilibrium.

According to Job's method (*loc. cit.*), different volumes of uranyl and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate were mixed in various ratios (0.1 - 1.0) of the concentration of uranyl ion to the total concentration of uranyl ion and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate. The p_H of the mixture solution was kept constant at 4.50 by the addition of alkali, keeping the total volume constant.

For the colorimetric measurements, turbid solutions were centrifuged to obtain clear solutions.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 represents the changes in the p_H when uranyl nitrate and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate, in different proportions, were titrated with alkali respectively. The 'a' values, plotted as abscissa are the number of equivalents of alkali added per mole of uranyl ion. Curves A, B, C and D are for $6.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ solutions in (i) uranyl nitrate (A), (ii) 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 mixtures of uranyl nitrate and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (B and C) and (iii) 1 : 1 mixture of uranyl nitrate and monosodium potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (D). Curves E and F are for $6.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ solutions of mercurisulphosalicylic acid and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate. When alkali is added to uranyl nitrate (A), no precipitation occurs until nearly two equivalents of alkali have been added (p_H 4.60).

The neutralisation of mercurisulphosalicylic acid (E) and its potassium chloride salt (F) has been discussed in an earlier communication (Singh and Prakash, *loc. cit.*, p. 197).

When one equivalent of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate is added to uranyl nitrate (B), the initial p_H (2.40) is slightly lower than that of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (2.60) or uranyl nitrate (3.32) alone. The mixture solution is orange-red in colour which deepens on the addition of alkali. The curve shows an inflection at $a = 2$, indicating the formation of a complex. Turbid solutions were obtained at p_H 7.0 and above with precipitation of uranyl hydroxide (at p_H 7.60). The reaction may be represented by

When two equivalents of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate are added to uranyl nitrate (C), an inflection occurs at $a = 3$, indicating that only one complex with 1 : 1 ratio is formed. No turbid solutions were obtained in this case and the precipitation occurred at p_H 9.20. The presence of an excess of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate thus appears to increase the stability of the complex formed.

FIG. 2

Filter Ks 54 (520-580 m μ) was used.

FIG. 1

Fig. 2 represents the changes in the colorimeter readings when $6.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ solutions of (i) 1 : 1 mixture of uranyl nitrate with potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (A) and its monosodium salt (C), and (ii) 1 : 2 mixture of uranyl nitrate and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (B) are titrated with alkali respectively. The abscissa represents the number of equivalents of alkali added (a). Curves A and C show a continuous rise with the addition of alkali, reaching a maximum value at $a = 2$ and $a = 1$ respectively, after which the values decrease rapidly. The maximum colorimeter reading is same in both the mixtures, as the same complex is formed. Curve B also shows a maximum at $a = 3$, but the value is greater than that obtained with 1 : 1 mixtures (A and C). Basing on the observation of Anderson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) that the uranyl sulphosalicylate complex exists in a partly dissociated state, the higher maximum value with the 1 : 2 mixture may be ascribed to the decreased dissociation of the complex formed. The maxima offer a clear evidence for the formation of only one complex of ratio 1 : 1, and for the displacement of phenolic hydrogen during complex formation. All the maxima occur at p_n 4.50, which indicates that the complex is formed at that p_n .

Fig. 3 represents the study of the composition of the complex by Job's method at a constant p_n of 4.50. The concentrations of the solutions were $2.00 \times 10^{-3}M$. The abscissa represents the ratio of the concentration of uranyl ion to the total concentration of uranyl ion and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate, i.e. $[UO_2^{2+}]/[UO_2^{2+}] + [pot. chloromercurisulphosalicylate]$. Consider the formation of a complex AB_n , where A is a metallic ion and B, a complexing agent :

FIG. 3

A—with filter Ks 47 (445-505 m μ).

B— " " Ks 54 (520-580 m μ).

are brought together in the ratios in which they exist in the complex (Martel and Calvin, "Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds", Prentice Hall, N.Y., p. 29, 1953). If the complex is the only coloured substance present, the optical density of the solution is proportional to the concentration of the complex. Hence, a plot of optical density

of the solutions were $2.00 \times 10^{-3}M$. The abscissa represents the ratio of the concentration of uranyl ion to the total concentration of uranyl ion and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate, i.e. $[UO_2^{2+}]/[UO_2^{2+}] + [pot. chloromercurisulphosalicylate]$. Consider the formation of a complex AB_n , where A is a metallic ion and B, a complexing agent :

$$K = [AB_n]/[A] \times [B]^n.$$

If we impose the restriction

$$[A] + [B] = C \text{ (constant),}$$

it can be shown that when AB_n is maximum

$$[B]/[A] = n \text{ or } \frac{d(AB_n)}{d(A)} = 0.$$

In other words, for a constant total concentration of metal and complexing agent, the concentration of the complex is greatest when the metal and complexing agent

and composition of solution under the restriction imposed would give a curve with a maximum at the composition corresponding to the formula of the complex.

In our experiments, though the uranyl nitrate was slightly coloured, it did not affect the colorimeter readings of the complex. From the graph it can be seen that, at a constant p_H of 4.50, the maximum occurs at 0.5 mole ratio of the concentration of uranyl ion to the total concentration of uranyl ion and potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate, which indicates the formation of a complex in which the molar ratio of metal ion to complexing agent is 1 : 1.

Fig. 4 represents the changes in the specific conductivity when $6.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ solutions in (i) uranyl nitrate (A), (ii) 1 : 1 mixture of uranyl nitrate with potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (B) and (iii) potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (D) were titrated with alkali respectively. The abscissa represents the equivalents of alkali added (a). D shows a minimum at $a = 1$, and a break at $a = 2$, which can be explained by the following equation :

The 1 : 1 mixtures of uranyl nitrate with potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate (B) show minima at $a = 2$ and $a = 1$ respectively, which indicates the displacement of the phenolic hydrogen during the complex formation.

Fig. 5 represents the changes in the p_H and colorimeter readings with the progressive addition of uranyl nitrate to monosodium salt of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate. The concentration of both the solutions were $6.25 \times 10^{-3}M$. A represents the p_H of the mixture, while A' is for uranyl nitrate alone at similar concentrations. B is the colorimeter reading for the mixture solution. With the addition of uranyl nitrate, the p_H of the monosodium salt (6.25) decreases rapidly and comes to nearly a constant value when one equivalent of uranyl nitrate has been added. It will be seen that A lies below A', which clearly indicates that there has been an increase in the H^+ ion concentration of the mixture. This can only be explained on the basis of the displacement of the phenolic hydrogen of potassium chloromercurisulphosalicylate :

This clearly shows that the phenolic hydrogen is displaced even in acidic medium (p_H 2.70).

FIG. 5

Filter Ks 54 (520-580 m μ) was used.

FIG. 4

The colorimeter reading curve (B) shows a gradual increase with the addition of uranyl nitrate and reaches almost a constant value when one equivalent has been added. It will be seen that with the addition of uranyl nitrate to monosodium potassium chloro-mercurisulphosalicylate, there is a decrease in the p_H value together with an increase in the colorimeter reading. This fact provides a more clear evidence that the phenolic hydrogen is displaced during complex formation. (Uranyl nitrate alone gives a negligible colorimeter reading.)

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